

COUPLED NON-ORTHOGONAL CONSTITUTIVE MODEL FOR WOVEN FABRIC COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

A coupled non-orthogonal constitutive model was newly proposed for woven fabric composites considering the conjoined effect of tensile and shear forces. The predictability of the developed model was examined and compared with the previous decoupled model for the bias-extension tests with various aspect ratios and inclined angle. It showed that the new model captures the physics of material deformation.

Keywords: Coupled non-orthogonal constitutive model, Tension-shear coupling, Woven fabric composites, Composite forming, Bias-extension test

INTRODUCTION

Since composite materials possess enhanced and multi-functional material properties, they have widely received intense attention in many advanced industrial areas such as aerospace, automotives and energy fields. Particularly, the woven fabric composite materials have significant structural capability to provide near-net-shape products due to possessing high formability and strength as well as ultra low weight.

As an efficient forming method, the thermo-stamping operation can be easily applied for the large scale production by significantly reducing manufacturing time and cost. Therefore, it is important to improve the prediction performance of numerical thermo-forming process for woven composite materials with accurate material models and simulation methods. Due to the large deformation of the woven fabric during the thermo-forming, the mechanical properties of woven fabric composites should be carefully examined to depict non-linear loading behaviors by the crimp interchange and the lateral compression between yarns.

During the past decades, many numerical techniques for thermo-forming simulations have been proposed. Event though the classical fishnet algorithm [1] based on the kinematics of woven composites was efficient and useful tool by significantly reducing the computational time, the mechanical properties of woven fabrics were ignored and therefore the prediction capability was insufficient. As a continuum-mechanics based approaches, meso-scale continuum models [2,3] can represent forming behavior of the

yarn structure in the unit cell by applying corresponding material properties. However, meso-scale continuum methods are not suitable for the forming simulation since numerous finite elements and huge computational costs are unavoidable. Therefore, shell/membrane element based macro-scale continuum methods are more efficient for the woven fabric forming calculation. Among several macro-scale models, non-orthogonal constitutive models [4,5] are able to effectively describe the non-linear and anisotropic material behaviors of the woven fabric composites by tracing the orientation change of yarns during the thermo-forming simulation.

The shear behavior of woven fabric composites in the non-orthogonal constitutive model has been mainly assumed to be independent on the tensions in yarns. Recent experimental results using picture frame tests in which tension forces can be applied along the yarns [6], however, showed that the in-plane tension in yarns increases the shear force.

In this study, the tension-induced shear and transverse-induced tensile moduli have been newly introduced to take account of the tensile effect on the shear behavior and the biaxial effect on the tensile behavior, respectively. Through the meso-scale FE simulations [7], material parameters were determined. The revised phenomenological model was then verified by comparing its prediction of the material behavior subjected to the tension-shear coupled tests from the meso-scale simulations. Furthermore, by comparing with the previous non-coupled model, the prediction capability was examined for the experimental bias-extension tests with various aspect ratios and inclined angles.

THEORY

Non-orthogonal Constitutive Model

In the non-orthogonal constitutive model [5], the constitutive relationship between the contravariant stress and the covariant strain is defined in the non-orthogonal material coordinate system , $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \tilde{\mathbf{D}} \cdot \tilde{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}$, in which equivalent contravariant elastic constants \tilde{D}_{ij} are determined by fitting with experiments or meso-scale analysis. Finally, the elastic matrix in the orthogonal system can be obtained using the transformation relationship between the global orthogonal coordinate and the non-orthogonal material coordinate.

Figure 1. Orthogonal and non-orthogonal coordinate systems

As shown in Fig. 1, the transformation tensor \mathbf{P} can be expressed by two geometric angles ψ and θ , as following.

$$\mathbf{P} = \begin{bmatrix} P_\alpha^\beta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\psi & \sin\psi \\ \cos(\psi + \theta) & \sin(\psi + \theta) \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Since the stress and strain relationship of the woven fabric composites are defined in the non-orthogonal material coordinate frame, the coordinate transformations of stress and strain into the orthogonal coordinate system should be considered in the non-orthogonal constitutive model as $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{T} \cdot \tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ and $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = \mathbf{T}^T \cdot \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ where

$$\mathbf{T} = \begin{bmatrix} (P_1^1)^2 & (P_2^1)^2 & 2P_1^1 P_2^1 \\ (P_1^2)^2 & (P_2^2)^2 & 2P_2^2 P_1^2 \\ P_1^1 P_2^1 & P_2^2 P_1^2 & P_1^2 P_2^1 + P_1^1 P_2^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Furthermore, the stress increment $d\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ in the FE calculation can be obtained from the Jacobian tensor $\partial\boldsymbol{\sigma}/\partial\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ as following.

$$\frac{\partial\boldsymbol{\sigma}}{\partial\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = \mathbf{T} \cdot \frac{\partial\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}}{\partial\tilde{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}} \cdot \mathbf{T}^T \quad (3)$$

Coupled Tensile and Shear Moduli

The constitutive relationship between stress and strain in the non-orthogonal material coordinate system can be rewritten as following matrix form.

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \tilde{\mathbf{D}} \cdot \tilde{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} \quad \text{or} \quad \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\sigma}^{11} \\ \tilde{\sigma}^{22} \\ \tilde{\sigma}^{12} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{D}^{11} & \tilde{D}^{12} & \tilde{D}^{13} \\ \tilde{D}^{21} & \tilde{D}^{22} & \tilde{D}^{23} \\ \tilde{D}^{31} & \tilde{D}^{32} & \tilde{D}^{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\varepsilon}_{11} \\ \tilde{\varepsilon}_{22} \\ \tilde{\gamma}_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

In this work, only diagonal terms in the contravariant stiffness matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{D}}$ were considered for the simplicity of the numerical formulation. Considering coupling effects, \tilde{D}^{11} , \tilde{D}^{22} and \tilde{D}^{33} can be written as following forms.

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{D}^{11} &= \tilde{D}_1(\tilde{\varepsilon}_{11}) \tilde{D}'_1(\tilde{\varepsilon}_{11}, \tilde{\varepsilon}_{22}) \\ \tilde{D}^{22} &= \tilde{D}_2(\tilde{\varepsilon}_{22}) \tilde{D}'_2(\tilde{\varepsilon}_{11}, \tilde{\varepsilon}_{22}) \\ \tilde{D}^{33} &= \tilde{G}(\tilde{\gamma}_{12}) \tilde{G}'(\tilde{\varepsilon}_{11}, \tilde{\varepsilon}_{22}, \tilde{\gamma}_{12}) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $\bar{\gamma}$ is the representative shear strain defined as $\bar{\gamma} = \bar{\gamma}_0(\bar{\gamma} - \bar{\gamma}_1)$. In Eq. (5), \tilde{D}_1 and \tilde{D}_2 represent pure tensile moduli in corresponding directions. \tilde{G} is a pure shear modulus which can be obtained from shear tests without tension. As for the coupling modifiers, \tilde{D}'_1 and \tilde{D}'_2 are transverse-induced tensile rigidities, and \tilde{G}' is a tension-induced shear rigidity. Finally, following formulae can be introduced for the coupled moduli of balanced fabrics.

$$\tilde{D}'_1 = 1 + a(\tilde{\varepsilon}_{11}) \left[\frac{\tilde{\varepsilon}_{22}}{\tilde{\varepsilon}_{11}} \right]^{b(\tilde{\varepsilon}_{11})}, \quad \tilde{D}'_2 = 1 + a(\tilde{\varepsilon}_{22}) \left[\frac{\tilde{\varepsilon}_{11}}{\tilde{\varepsilon}_{22}} \right]^{b(\tilde{\varepsilon}_{22})}, \quad \tilde{G}' = 1 + p(\bar{\gamma}) \left[\frac{\tilde{\varepsilon}_{11} + \tilde{\varepsilon}_{22}}{\bar{\varepsilon}_0} \right]^{q(\bar{\gamma})} \quad (6)$$

Hypoelastic Constitutive Model for Meso-scale Analysis

In this work, the meso-scale FE analysis was performed based on the hypoelastic constitutive model [7] in order to measure the material parameters. In this model, the constitutive equation becomes $\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \mathbf{C} : \mathbf{D}$ where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and \mathbf{D} are Cauchy stress and strain rate tensors while \mathbf{C} is a stiffness tensor. The objective derivative of the derivative stress tensor $\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ is defined as

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \mathbf{Q} \cdot \frac{d}{dt} (\mathbf{Q}^T \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{Q}) \cdot \mathbf{Q}^T \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{Q} is the rotation tensor of the material. Also, for providing the proper boundary conditions to represent the periodic structure of the unit cell, the kinematic condition should be carefully imposed along the geometric boundaries. Therefore, the periodic fluctuation should become identical on the paired material points on two opposite boundaries and the fluctuation at the corners of the unit cell should be removed to avoid the rigid body movement.

MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION

Meso-scale FE Analysis

In order to determine mechanical properties in the non-orthogonal model, meso-scale FE simulations were carried out for the balanced plain woven fabric composites considering 8.0mm x 8.0mm unit cell model of 0.78mm thick woven fabric. To determine the pure tensile and shear moduli, uni-axial tensile and pure shear tests were carried out, respectively. As for the transverse-induced tensile and the tension-induced shear moduli, even bi-axial tensile and shear tests under even bi-axial tension mode were considered respectively.

Pure Tensile and Shear Moduli

Through the meso-scale FE analysis, the force-displacement data were converted into stress and strain, and following data-fit equations were obtained

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{D}_\alpha \text{ (MPa)} &= \frac{d_0}{1 + \exp[-d_1 (\tilde{\varepsilon}_{\alpha\alpha} - d_2)]} \\ \tilde{G} \text{ (MPa)} &= g_0 + g_1 \exp(g_2 \tilde{\gamma}_{12}) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where α is 1 or 2 without summation and the obtained parameters d_i and g_i were summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Parameters for pure tensile and shear moduli

Pure tensile modulus		Pure shear modulus	
d_0	18000.0	g_0	3.37×10^{-5}
d_1	650.0	g_1	8.19×10^{-7}
d_2	4.79×10^{-3}	g_2	14.1

Transverse-induced Tensile and Tensile-induced Shear Moduli

As for the transverse-induced tensile modulus, the meso-scale FE simulation was performed for the bi-axial tension tests with several different strain ratios ($k = \tilde{\varepsilon}_{22}/\tilde{\varepsilon}_{11}$); 0.5, 1.0 and 2.0. By minimizing the deviation of fit data, a and b in Eq. (6) were determined as following equations.

$$\begin{aligned} a(\tilde{\varepsilon}_{\alpha\alpha}) &= (51.0 + 18430.0 \exp[-655.7 \tilde{\varepsilon}_{\alpha\alpha}]) \tilde{\varepsilon}_{\alpha\alpha}^{1.25} \\ b(\tilde{\varepsilon}_{\alpha\alpha}) &= 0.9 + 1.3 \exp[-563.4 \tilde{\varepsilon}_{\alpha\alpha}] \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where α is 1 or 2, and not on summation.

In order to determine the tension-induced shear modulus, shear tests under even bi-axial tension mode ($k=1$) were performed at four different tensile strain levels; 0.1%, 0.2%, 0.3% and 0.4%. There are two stages in the simulation. In the first step, bi-axial tension test is carried out and then the shear test is performed as holding the tensile strain amount. As shown in Fig. 2, there are two stiff deflecting points in each curve. Using these deflecting points, the representative strain $\bar{\gamma}$ was determined with

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\gamma}_0 &= 1.0 + 0.015 \exp[560.4(\tilde{\varepsilon}_{11} + \tilde{\varepsilon}_{22})] \\ \bar{\gamma}_1 &= 25000(\tilde{\varepsilon}_{11} + \tilde{\varepsilon}_{22})^{2.5} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Furthermore, tensile-induced shear modulus was obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\varepsilon}_0 &= 0.001 \\ p(\bar{\gamma}) &= 3.9 + 2778.3 \exp(-459.7 \bar{\gamma}) + 284.6 \exp(-34.6 \bar{\gamma}) \\ q(\bar{\gamma}) &= \frac{3.2}{1 + \exp[9.5(\bar{\gamma} - 0.65)]} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Using obtained parameters, macro-scale FEM simulations were performed for same meso-scale FE tests. As shown in Fig. 3 as solid lines, simulation results fit well with meso-scale analysis results.

Figure 2. Bi-axial tension and shear tests with bi-axial tension

VERIFICATION

Shear Tests Under Uni-axial and Uneven Bi-axial Tension Modes

In order to verify the developed model using coupled moduli, the shear tests under uniaxial and un-even biaxial tensions have been performed. The predicted behaviors were also compared with the meso-scale analysis results. For the shear tests under uniaxial tension mode, four different tensile strain levels were considered; 0.1%, 0.2%, 0.3% and 0.4%. For the un-even biaxial mode, two cases for 0.1%-0.2% and 0.2%-0.4% were predicted. Both meso-scale analysis and the prediction results were shown in Fig. 3. The prediction agreed very well with the meso-scale analysis results.

Experimental Bias-extension Tests

The new phenomenological material model was also used to predict the mechanical behavior for the bias-extension tests with various aspect ratios and tilted angle. Here, two different aspect ratios were considered as 1:1, 1:2 for initially 45° and 27° aligned to the loading axis. As shown in Fig. 4, when the different ratio and inclined angle from the original bias-extension test were considered, the coupled effects were dominant so that the newly developed model showed better prediction results than the previous model.

Figure 3. Shear tests under uniaxial and uneven biaxial tension modes

Figure 4. Comparison between uncoupled and coupled non-orthogonal constitutive models for bias-extension tests

CONCLUSIONS

In order to take account of the bi-axial effect on the tensile modulus and the tensile effect on the shear modulus during the composite forming, the non-orthogonal constitutive model has been improved so that the transverse coupled tensile and the tension coupled shear modulus was newly introduced in the material stiffness matrix. From the meso-scale FE analysis results, the material properties were determined and implemented into the revised numerical user code. To examine the prediction performance of the developed model, tensile tests under even and uneven biaxial tension modes, the shear tests under uni-axial, even and uneven biaxial tension modes, and bias-extension tests with different aspect ratios and tilted angles were carried out. The prediction results showed very good agreement with the meso-scale analysis and experimental test results.

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